

A STUDY ON THE GLOBAL EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG THE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN KAKCHING AND THOUBAL DISTRICT OF MANIPUR

¹Madhu Chaubey, ²Limpi Talukdar, ³Ranjan Kumar

¹Research Scholar, Department of education, Manipur University, Canchipur, India, madhupravespathak@gmail.com

²Research Scholar, Department of education, Manipur University, Canchipur, India, limpitalukdar92@gmail.com

³Research Scholar, Department of Education, Manipur University, Canchipur, India, ranjan5430053@gmail.com

Abstract

“Emotional Intelligence is the ability to sense, understand, value and effectively apply the power of emotions as a source of human energy, information, trust, creativity and influence

-DANIEL GOLEMAN

Emotional intelligence which is also known as emotional quotient is the ability to manage our own emotion by understanding thing in positive ways. It helps in relieving stress, overcome challenges of the life, defusing the tension, and developing empathy towards others. It refers to the ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotion. It helps in developing an ability to handle pressure and anxiety. It is actually a meta-level ability which helps in managing themselves internally. The objective of the present study is to know the global emotional intelligence of students in relation to the variables:-1) Boys and Girls 2) Science and arts, 3) Joint and nuclear family, 4) Small and large family. The researcher in the present study collected data from 503 respondents using descriptive survey method and analysed using t-test. The findings of the study- there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of boys and girls student and also science and arts student. But significant difference is observed when analyse between joint and nuclear family also between small and large family.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, tension, meta-level, anxiety.

INTRODUCTION

The term emotional intelligence is the combination of two of the three domains ie, cognitive and affective. It is the ability to think creatively and to use our emotions to solve the problems. Usually the emotional intelligent person have following ability ie, to control emotion, to regulate emotion, to understand emotion and to identify emotions. It is to an extent a recent term which comes in the knowledge of the people. According to some researcher is that it is an inborn ability while some considered it as an acquired ability which can also be strengthened. If a person has high emotional intelligence it means he/she has a strong ability to express the emotion in healthy

manner and can also understand the emotions of the friends which may enhance the relationship between the two.

The term emotional intelligence was originally developed during 1970s and 1980s by Howard Gardner, Peter salovey and John Mayer. In the doctoral dissertation of Wayne Leon Payne in1985 the term emotional intelligence first appeared in his book entitled “A Study of Emotion: Developing Emotional Intelligence”. Later Daniel Goleman, wrote the pioneering book on emotional intelligence. It actually triggered due to many frustrating business meeting with her wife ‘Tara’ result in co-authored with his wife on the study. In 1995 Goleman in his book claims that only 20% of the

Person's success can be attributed to IQ. This prompts researcher and academicians to find out other factors which contribute 80% of the success of the individual. Its Goleman's 1st book which actually create new area of the problem to be studied not only in the field of education but also in other areas like business, career development, industrial and organizational psychology and many more. Many professional are curious to know how emotional intelligence impacts the performance of the individual. Low and Nelson (2006) claim that EQ is crucial to a student's personal growth and success. They claimed that student with emotional intelligence skill can cope up in the demanding situation in a best possible manner. Emotional intelligence means perceptual capacity, tool, recognition, application and management of emotion in self and others (Myre, 1997). In some studies, emotional intelligence correlates positively with academic achievement (Parker, 2004). The concept of emotional intelligence can be applied in educational situations. One of the reasons for dealing with emotional intelligence is that emotional intelligence compared its traditional concept, intelligence quotient, is accounted as a better predictor for social achievements (Golman, 1995). Individuals with high emotional skills have better social skills, more stable long term relations and more ability to solve problems. Children with high emotional skills more capable of concentrating on problems and using problem solving skill that increase their cognitive abilities (Soltanifar, 2007). Studying the relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement is very challenging and studies done in this respect are often contradictory. Results of some studies such as those by Barket and Saluvi (2004), Elias.et.al (2003), Samari and Tahmasbi (2007), Besharat.et.al (2006) showed the relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement . Results of some studies such as those by Lavasani.et.al (2007), Koohsar.et.al (2007) showed that there is no significant relation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. According to Brodi and Hal who studied emotional differences between male and female genders, females replace emotional reaction with hand to hand combat better than males. On the contrary, males do not show their feelings and are not aware from emotional state of themselves and others. In this direction, Besharat.et.al (2006) reported

emotional intelligence of female students higher than that in, male students. . It is evident that is is not reasonable to considered emotional skills without paying attention to psychological personal dimension

Review of related literature

Bar-On's (1997) "The Bar-On Emotional Quotient Inventory: A test of Emotional Intelligence" this study portrays social responsibility and empathy as specific interpersonal skills. Goleman's 1995 model includes the same empathic awareness and attainment, this is a skill required to recognised emotions in others. Knowing there varying EI models the study of the relationship of EI to moral/ethical behaviour and to values has been inconsistent. The moral/ethical/value dimensions are often described as part of the basis for educational programs involving EI a well designed empirical research in this area is very much necessary.

Goleman (1998) "Working with emotional intelligence" Competency research in over 200 companies and organizations worldwide shows that about one-third of the difference is due to technical skill and cognitive ability while two-thirds is due to emotional competence. (In top leadership positions, over four-fifths of the difference is due to emotional competence).

Carmeli and Josman (2006) " The relationship among emotional intelligence, task performance, and organizational citizenship behaviours" this research suggested possible connections between emotional intelligence and positive performance in the workplace. Researchers say that even though research suggested that there is a connection between emotional intelligence and positive performance in the work place, it is typically based on self reported assessment and it overlooks that work performance is actually multidimensional. Research suggest that possible connection that possible connections between emotional intelligence and positive performance in work place. Authors noted that task performance may not reveal the completeness of a leader's work role. Other behaviours like maintain civil relationship and helping subordinates with issues would also influence the work performance. Researchers explored two essentials of the leader: altruism and general

compliance could be the reason that maintain the leader's respect from subordinates and could, therefore impact the subordinate willingness to conscientiously perform work for the leader. Researchers conducted a study on 215 employees in different 66 organisations in Israel to see if there was a connection between emotional intelligence with both altruistic behaviour and compliant behaviour. Data was collected from subordinates and supervisors, as well as the participants, themselves. Their findings suggest that both altruism and compliance were related to task performance. Researchers also found that three elements of EI (appraisal and expression of emotions, regulation of emotions, and utilization of emotions) were related to task performance and to altruistic behaviours, but only partially to compliance behaviours.

Koman, E. S., & Wolff, S.B. (2008) "Emotional intelligence competencies in the team and team leader: A multi-level examination of the impact of emotional intelligence on team performance". This study examines the relationship between team leader EI competencies and team performance". The study was conducted on 349 aircrew and maintenance military team members participated representing 81 aircrew and maintenance teams. Results shows that team leader EI is significantly related to the presence of emotionally competent group norms (ECGN) on the teams they lead, and that ECGN are related to team performance. The authors also provide three suggestions. Firstly, employee leaders with better EI competencies not only increase their own personal performance but also of the teams they lead. Secondly, by developing or hiring emotionally competencies managers. Finally by developing emotionally competent first line leaders, organizations should develop emotional competent executive leaders because each individual on the executive management team influences the development of ECGNs on the teams he or she leads.

Hopkins & Bilimoria (2008) in his study "Social and Emotional Competencies Predicting Success for Male and Female Executives" explored the relationship emotional and social intelligence competencies and organizational success. The study illustrates not much of differences between male and female leaders in their demonstration of emotional and social intelligence competencies and also found that

when it comes to competency demonstration most successful men and women were more the same than difference. However gender did play a reasonable role in the relationship between the demonstrations of these competencies and success. Further male leaders were considered to be more successful, even though male and female leaders demonstrated the same level of competencies. The four competencies that divided the most successful male and female leaders from their typical counterparts were self confidence, Achievement Orientation, Inspirational Leadership and Change Catalyst.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the present study is to examine the global emotional intelligence (EI/EQ) of students in relation to the following variables:

- a) To find out the difference between the emotional intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students.
- b) To find out the difference between the emotional intelligence of science and arts stream students of secondary school.
- c) To find out the difference between the emotional intelligence of joint and nuclear family of secondary school students.
- d) To find out the difference between the emotional intelligence of small and large family of secondary school students.

Hypothesis of the study

- a) There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of between boys and girls of secondary school.
- b) There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of science and arts secondary school students.
- c) There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of secondary school students who belongs to joint and nuclear family.
- d) There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of secondary school students who have small and large family.

Methodology of the study

In view of the objectives of the present study, the investigator has adopted the descriptive survey method since it helps us to understand the situation which exists at present. The population of the present study covers 503 respondents from various secondary school students which include Kakching, Sugnu, Langmeidong, Royal Academy, Chaoyaima, Lilong, and Heirok secondary schools which come under Kakching and Thoubal district of Manipur.

Tools used in the study

The instrument which helps to collect data from the sample is a tool. In the present study, the investigator used Emotional Intelligence Quotient tool devised by Upinder Dhar (Vice Chancellor, J.K. Lakshmi Pat University Jaipur), Anukool Hyde (Assistant Professor Shri Vaishnav Institute of Management, Indor), Sanjyot Pethe (Lecturer, Nirmal Institute of Management, Ahmedabad) and was published under National psychological corporation. The emotional quotient consists of 34 items which comes under A to J factors. The investigator conducted this tool with secondary school students of Kakching and Thoubal district.

Sample and sampling technique

The current study was the secondary school students of Kakching and Thoubal district of Manipur. The sample was recruited randomly from 503 respondents of secondary school students.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATION

Data Analysis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of between boys and girls of secondary school.

Table: 1 Mean and S.D of emotional intelligence and gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	t-test	d.f.	p-value
Boys	182	130.85	16.24	0.023	501	0.982
Girls	321	130.81	15.04			

**t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table: It was detected from the table that the mean score of emotional intelligence between male and female higher secondary school students in the present study were found to be 130.85 and 130.81, respectively. The mean variation was minimal and when applied t-test it was found to be insignificant relationship between gender and emotional intelligence as manifested by p-value of 0.982.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of science and arts secondary school students.

Table: 2 Mean and S.D of emotional intelligence and stream of subject

Stream of subject	N	Mean	Std. D	t-test	d.f.	p-value
Arts	70	131.00	13.88	0.102	501	0.919
Science	433	130.80	15.72			

**t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table: It was perceived from the table that the mean score of emotional intelligence between arts and science higher secondary school students in the present study were found to be 131.00 and 130.80 respectively. The mean variation was negligible and when applied t-test it was found to be insignificant relationship between stream of subject and emotional intelligence as marked by p-value of 0.919.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of secondary school students who belongs to joint and nuclear family.

Table: 3 Mean and S.D of emotional intelligence and types of family

Types of family	N	Mean	Std. D	t-test	d.f.	p-value
Joint Family	246	132.95	14.59	3.034	501	0.003**
Nuclear Family	257	128.79	16.03			

**t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table: It was viewed from the table that the mean score of emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students belonged to joint and nuclear family were 132.95 and 128.79 respectively. The mean variation was maximal and when applied t-test it was found to be have high significant relationship between types of family and emotional intelligence as evident by p-value = 0.003. The finding indicated that

student belonged to joint family were having higher emotional intelligence when compared to students belonged to nuclear family.

Hypothesis:4 There is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of secondary school students who have small and large family.

Table: 4 Mean and S.D of emotional intelligence and types of family

Family size	N	Mean	Std. D	t-test	d.f.	p-value
Small family size	234	128.31	16.796	3.434	501	0.001**
Large family size	269	133.01	13.885			

**t-test is highly significant at 0.01 levels

* t-test is significant at 0.05 levels

Table: It was discovered from the table that the mean score of emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students having small family size and large family size were 128.31 and 133.01 respectively. The mean variation was maximal and when applied t-test it was found to have highly significant relationship between family size and emotional intelligence as manifest by p-value = 0.001. The finding indicated that student belonged to large family size were having higher emotional intelligence when compared to student from small family size.

3) It is found that there is a significant difference in higher secondary school students from joint to nuclear family on their emotional intelligence.

4) It is found that there is a significant difference in higher secondary school students from small to large family on their emotional intelligence.

Educational Implication

Hence, it is suggested that every institution may think over implementing emotional intelligence to enhance the capability, quality, competency and ability of the school going students.

Findings

The following are the findings of the study:-

- 1) It is found that the emotional intelligence of both boys and girls of higher secondary school students are quite equal.
- 2) It is found that the stream does not impact emotional intelligence mean there is no significant difference between the emotional intelligence of science or arts stream students.

Conclusions

An emotion is not alone a part of intellect but is something which is the combination of both physical and psychological response an individual gives in a particular situation. In order to ensure emotional development, emotional intelligence must be includes as a part of school curriculum. With the implementation of emotional intelligence, noticeable progress can observe in personal, educational, and social life

of an individual. It will also help student to discontinue the mistake that a student made due to the lack of emotional intelligence. School which is the second home and a miniature society can play a vital role in shaping the future citizen. In order to improve the emotional intelligence an educational institution must include yoga in its school curriculum along with recruiting a yoga teacher. Educational institution must ensure that they recruit the faculty who have high emotional intelligence as teacher are actually the role model of every student.

Reference

- [1] Bar-On, R (1997). The Bar-On Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-I): A test of emotional interlligence .
- [2] Carmeli, A., & Josman, Z.E. (2006). The relationship among emotional intelligence, task performance organizational citizenship behaviours. *Human Performance*, 19, 403-419
- [3] Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. New York: Bantam Books
- [4] Hopkins, M.M., Bilimoria, D. (2008). Social and Emotional Competencies predicting Success for Male and Female Executives (1 ed., vol.27). *Journal of Management Development*.
- [5] Koman, E.S., Wolff, S.B., (2008). Emotional intelligence competencies in the team leader: A multi-level examination of the impact of emotional intelligence on team performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 27 (1)
- [6] Low, G.R. & Nelson, D.B. (2006, October 18-21). Emotional Intelligence and college success: A Research- based assessment and intervention. Paper presented at the 39th Annual Conference of the college reading and learning Association and the 25th Annual Conference of college Academic Support Programs, Austin, Texas. Retrieved December 9, 2009, from http://www.tamuk.edu/edu/kwei000/Research/Articles/Articles_files/EI_and_College_Success-2006_cederpaper.pdf
- [7] Samari, A, Tahmasbi, F, (2007). Studying emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students, quarterly of mental health principles,
- [8] Besharat, M, Shalchi, B, Shamsipour H,(2006). The relation between emotional intelligence and students' academic success, new educative thoughts quarterly.
- [9] Qolamali Lavasani, M, Keivanzadeh, H, (2007). The relation of academic activity, advancement incentive, emotional intelligence and contextual variables with students' academic achievement, magazine of psychology and educative science,
- [10] Kouhsar, A, Roshan, R, Asqarnejad A, (2007). Comparative study of the relation between emotional intelligence and mental health and academic achievement in Shahed and state students of Tehran University, magazine of psychology and educative science.
- [11] Brackett MA, Salovey P. Measuring (2004). Emotional intelligence with Mayer-Salovey Caruso emotional intelligence test (MSCEIT). In : Geher G., Editor. *Measuring emotional intelligence: Common round and controversy*. Hauppauge, NY:Novel Science;
- [12] Elisas MJ, Gara M, Schuyere B. (2003). The promotion of social competence: Longitudinal study of a preventive school-based program. *American J Orthopsychiat*.; 61 (3):409-17
- [13] Goleman D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: The theory in practice*. New York: Basic Books;
- [14] Parker JDA, Summerfeldt LJ, Hogan MJ, Majeski SA. (2004). Emotional intelligence and academic success. Examine the transition from high school to university. *Personal Individ Diff*.,36 (1): 163-72.
- [15] Maryer JD, Salovey P. What (1997). Is emotional intelligence? In: Salovey P, Sluyter DJ, editors. *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications*. New York: Basic Books; pp.3-31.